

D3.8 - LIBS technology for elemental analysis of water - hardware photos and description

prepared for

WP3.4 - Water Quality and Condition Monitoring

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Executive summary

This document presents photos of the hardware bought and created to build the Laser Induced Breakdown Spectroscopy hardware for the purpose of water quality and condition monitoring. Hardware is presented in state as for 31.01.2024.

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1 Description of LIBS subsystem

The figure below presents the internal architecture of LIBS subsystem, that is part of the Water Quality and Condition Monitoring system. The water flows through the system, looking on the figure, from left to right. The measurement takes place within enclosed laser compartment – because of the laser safety reasons. Powerful 300mJ laser pulse turns droplet of water inside transparent measurement cell into plasma, which emits radiation when cooled down. Analysing that emission, we can learn the elemental composition of the sample – that how the LIBS technology work in our case. The emitted light is observed by the Ocean FX spectrometer and the spectral data is later analysed by the software on the PC. The PC is brain of the system – it commands the laser and spectrometer, analyses the data and communicates with the rest of LUWEX system through the means of digital I/O card. Internal power distribution unit is responsible for powering the system’s elements.

Figure 1-1 LIBS subsystem for LUWEX architecture

2 Hardware for LIBS subsystem

2.1 Items with pending delivery

Items still not delivered:

1. hydraulic hose and coupling elements,
2. VITON seals,
3. safety markings,
4. safety lamp,
5. water chambers
6. elements of internal power distribution subsystem,
7. measurement cell.

2.2 Delivered items

Figure 2-1 Laser power supply

Figure 2-2 Laser chiller

Figure 2-3 Laser LPS-1064-S-300mJ (in protective bag)

Figure 2-4 Laser chiller filter

Figure 2-5 Laser protective glasses

Figure 2-6 Laser compartment

Figure 2-7 Optical system inside laser chamber (not fully assembled)

Figure 2-8 Other optical elements

Figure 2-9 Water pump for testing

Figure 2-10 Safety elements (emergency button, safety lock, limit switches)

Figure 2-11 Other mechanical elements

Figure 2-12 Ocean-FX -XR1-ES spectrometer

Figure 2-13 Industrial PC for controlling the system

Figure 2-14 I/O PC card (installed into PC)

Figure 2-15 Dell P2422H display (to be used with PC)